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СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Гульмухамедов Пулат, Ризаев Жасур, Хабилов Нигмон, Бобоев Кодиржон ПОЛИМОРФНЫЕ ГЕНЫ ЦИКЛА ФОЛАТОВ И ВРОЖДЕННЫЕ ПОРОКИ ЧЕЛЮСТНО-ЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	6
2. Бекмуродов Мухаммад, Абдирашидова Гулноза, Олимжонова Фарахноза ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ТАКТИКИ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ НОСОВЫХ КРОВОТЕЧЕНИЙ.....	10
3. Vuzrukzoda Javoxirxon, Rizaev Elyor, Olimjonov Kamron JAG‘LAR SUYAK TO‘QIMASINING ATROFIYASI SHAROITIDA SUYAKNING YO‘NALTIRILGAN REGENERATSIYASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	13
4. Хамракулова Наргиза, Хушвакова Нилуфар, Ахмедова Мафтуна ТИМПАНОПЛАСТИКА УТКАЗГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА КВИН ТЕРАПИЯНИНГ КЛИНИК НАМОЁН БУЛИШИ ВА БЕМОР ҲАЁТ ТАРЗИГА ТАДБИК ЭТИШ.....	19
5. Гавхар Арипова, Наргизахон Абдукадырова, Шахноза Расулова, Эльбек Насимов, Саида Машарипова СОЗДАНИЕ ЦИФРОВОГО МЕТОДА ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ШИРИНЫ ЗУБНЫХ РЯДОВ.....	23
6. Ulug‘bekova Gulruh, Maxsudova Hakimaxon, Adhamov Shohjahon 7-12 YOSH TOIFASIDAGI BOLALAR DAKRIAL KO‘RSATKICHLARINING TAHLILI.....	28
7. Гульмухамедов Пулат, Ризаев Жасур, Хабилов Нигмон, Бобоев Кодиржон ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВСТРЕЧАЕМОСТИ АЛЛЕЛЬНОГО ПОЛИМОРФИЗМА Ile462Val В ГЕНЕ CYP1A1 СРЕДИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ВРОЖДЕННЫМИ ПОРОКАМИ ЧЕЛЮСТНО-ЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	31
8. Гулямов Шерзод, Карабаев Хуррам, Хамракулова Наргиза СПОСОБЫ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВРОЖДЕННОЙ АТРЕЗИИ НАРУЖНОГО СЛУХОВОГО ПРОХОДА.....	37
9. Isayev Umid, Olimjonov Kamron TISH OLDIRGAN BEMORLARDA OLINGAN TISHLAR BO‘LAGIDAN FOYDALANIB KATAKNI YOPILISH USULI VA QON LAXTAGI OSTIDA TISH KATAGINING BITISH BOSQICHILARINI QIYOSIY TAQQOSLASH.....	42
10. Narzieva Dilfuza, Radjabiy Muzayanna IMPROVING THE TREATMENT OF PERI-IMPLANTITIS USING THE HERBAL MEDICINE ZUB-PRE.....	47
11. Исхакова Зухро, Шомурадov Кахрамон, Раджабий Музаянна ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА ГНОЙНО-ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЧЕЛЮСТНО-ЛИЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	50

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ТИМПАНОПЛАСТИКА УТКАЗГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА КВИН ТЕРАПИЯНИНГ КЛИНИК НАМОЁН БУЛИШИ ВА БЕМОР ХАЁТ ТАРЗИГА ТАДБИК ЭТИШИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Хозирги вақтда сурункали йирингли отит касалликларини даволашнинг энг самарали усули жаррохлик ҳисобланади: тимпаноластика. Клиникамизда тимпаноластика самарадорлигини ошириш учун қоннинг вена ичига нурланиши (КВИН) қўлланилади. Қоннинг вена ичига нурланиши усули ёрдамида операциядан кейинги соҳада репаратив жараёнларга нурланиш таъсири остида ногора парданинг микроциркуляцияси даражасининг ошиши ўрганилди.

Калит сўзлар: йирингли отит, тимпаноластика, қоннинг вена ичига нурланиши, гемостаз кўрсаткичлари, касаллик фаолияти.

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ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ВЛОК-ТЕРАПИИ НА КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ И КАЧЕСТВО ЖИЗНИ БОЛЬНЫХ ПОСЛЕ ПЕРЕНЕСЕННОЙ ТИМПАНОПЛАСТИКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время наиболее эффективным методом лечения хронического гнойного среднего отита является хирургический: тимпаноластика. В нашей клинике для повышения эффективности тимпаноластики применяется внутривенное облучение крови (ВЛОК). С помощью метода внутривенного облучения крови изучено повышение уровня микроциркуляции барабанной перепонки при воздействии лазерного облучения крови на репаративные процессы в послеоперационной области.

Ключевые слова: гнойный средний отит, тимпаноластика, внутривенное лазерное облучение крови, показатели гемостаза, активность заболевания.

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APPLICATION OF ILBI -THERAPY ON CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS AFTER POSTED TYMPANOPLASTY

ANNOTATION

Currently, the most effective treatment for chronic suppurative otitis media is surgical: tympanoplasty. In our clinic, intravenous laser blood irradiation (ILBI) is used to increase the efficiency of tympanoplasty. Using the method of intravenous blood irradiation, an increase in the level of microcirculation of the tympanic membrane was studied under the influence of laser irradiation of blood on reparative processes in the postoperative area.

Key words: purulent otitis media, tympanoplasty, intravenous laser blood irradiation, hemostasis indicators, disease activity.

Chronic inflammatory diseases of the middle ear occupy one of the significant places in otorhinolaryngology and have, in addition to medical, a great social value. This is due to the fact that these diseases are not only one of the most common among chronic diseases of the ENT organs, but also one of the main causes of hearing loss and severe intracranial complications, an unfavorable outcome of the course of the patient's disease. The prevalence of chronic purulent otitis media remains high to date - 13.7-20.9 per 1000 population and has no tendency to decrease. Among the causes of high degree of hearing loss,

the share of chronic purulent otitis media and their consequences - adhesive otitis media occurs up to 18.5%, and in the structure of the population's appeal for hearing - improving care-23-24%, respectively. [9].

Currently, surgical treatment of this disease is the most effective: it not only contributes to the rehabilitation of the pathological focus, but also provides reconstruction of sound-conducting elements, restoration of the closed tympanic cavity. This allows you to improve your hearing, as well as prevent relapses of the disease. To date, we have accumulated

considerable experience in performing various types of tympanoplasty. However, there is not always a permanent closure of the perforation of the tympanic membrane.

According to the literature, the occurrence of re-perforation is observed in 7-57% of cases [6, 7]. This determines the urgency of finding modern methods of patient management that could reduce the frequency of adverse outcomes. One of the reasons for complete or partial rejection of the neotympanic membrane after tympanoplasty is a violation of microcirculation in the surgical area. As a result of vascular damage in the area of surgery and, as a result, their reflex spasm, there is a violation of the formation of capillary blood supply and trophic innervation of the graft, which can lead to its partial or complete necrosis [3, 4].

There are several ways to improve the effectiveness of tympanoplasty. The main efforts of otosurgeons are aimed at improving surgical techniques and techniques of tamponade, minimizing surgical trauma. Another area of prevention of complications is the impact on the course of reparative processes in the postoperative period, the creation of more favorable conditions for the engraftment of the flap, including the normalization of microcirculation processes. For this purpose, some authors suggest using systemic vasoactive drugs and nootropics, the action of which is aimed at eliminating microcirculatory disorders [8]. Magnetotherapy and low-energy laser treatment are applied locally to the postoperative area [1, 5]. To improve the regeneration processes, the neotympanic flap is covered with various materials that stimulate the reparative processes: chitosan, biosynthetic wound coatings [5, 7].

One of the most effective new physiotherapy techniques is intravenous laser blood irradiation (VLOK). Due to the breadth of drug exposure, today this method is used to treat a number of disorders and diseases.

The essence of LOCK therapy is the effect on blood cells of photo energy using a laser LED inserted into a vein. In the course of actions, blood cells, passing through the area treated with a laser, receive a powerful stimulating charge that increases their viability, metabolic activity, and increases their oxygen, transport, defense, and other functions.

This technique is carried out in many areas of medicine, is widely used, for example, in surgery - to accelerate the healing of burns, wounds, trophic ulcers, with vascular lesions – phlebitis, arteritis, to prevent sepsis, bacteremia, viremia. The method of laser blood purification is a "miracle drug" for the body, which, in combination with traditional therapy, will make up for the immune deficiency, reduce cholesterol, increase the rheological properties of the blood and reduce the recovery time by 2-3 times. VLOK is a newly developed unique method developed on the device, together with the Research Center "Matrix" and the State Center for Laser Medicine-the laser therapeutic device "Matrix-VLOK" provides exposure to radiation with several wavelengths (from 0.36 to 0.9 microns) and a power of 1 to 35 MW,

which provides the most effective treatment modes. The procedure is quite comfortable and painless, which allows it to be carried out for children from 6 years old. The course consists of 7-15 daily procedures, but after the first session, patients note the recovery of general well-being. The healing effect lasts from 4 to 6 months.

The aim of the study was to study the effect of VLOK on some indicators of the quality of life of patients with chronic purulent otitis media after tympanoplasty.

Material and methods. In the private clinic SAOMED, the first studies were conducted on the use of VLOK therapy in patients who underwent tympanoplasty.

34 people aged from 5 to 60 years were examined. Patients of the control group (n = 15) received standard drug therapy with the use of basic anti-inflammatory drugs, patients of the main group (n = 19) received a course of intravenous laser therapy in addition to basic treatment. The course of intravenous laser therapy was carried out using the Matrix-VLOK device with alternating every other day the radiating head of the CL-VLOK with a wavelength of 635 nm, the output power of a single-use light guide of 1.5 – 2.0 MW-for 15 minutes, and the laser head of the CL-VLOK – 365 for UFOC with a wavelength of 365 nm-for 5 minutes. The procedures were performed daily, for 10 days.

The examination included the determination of activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT), prothrombin time (PTV), thrombin time (TV test), activity of the protein C system, antithrombin III. The dynamics and effectiveness of the therapy were evaluated using the DAS28 index.

The diagnosis of CHC was established on the basis of clinical, laboratory and instrumental methods of investigation, including complaints, anamnesis, objective data, clinical and biochemical blood tests and, according to indications, magnetic resonance computed tomography of the temporal bone.

The assessment of the quality of life was carried out using a general international questionnaire at three observation points - at admission, after 2 weeks and after 3 months. The 36 items of the questionnaire are grouped into 5 scales: physical functioning, role-playing activity, physical pain, general health, and vitality.

The obtained data were processed by the method of variation statistics. They are presented in the form of the arithmetic mean (M), the standard error of the arithmetic mean (m). The reliability of the differences was evaluated using the Student's criterion: the differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. In CSF, clinical manifestations may have different characteristics (Table 1). Before the start of treatment, complaints were detected: ear pain - in 69.9% of patients, purulent discharge from the ear - in 52.6% of patients, dizziness - in 23.6% of patients, nystagmus - 4.2% of patients and tinnitus-54.7% of patients. The provoking factor was most often frequent inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses.

Characteristics of clinical symptoms in patients with HCG

Clinical sign	%
Ear pain	69,9
For purulent discharge from the ear	52,6
For vertigo	23,6
On nystagmus	4,2
Tinnitus	54,7

Against the background of treatment, all patients experienced an improvement in well-being and decreased the severity of pain syndrome, as well as dizziness, ear noise and nystagmus (Table 2). In the control group, pain relief occurred after 22.3 ± 1.7 days, and ear noise after 21.4 ± 1.6 days. However, in patients receiving complex therapy

with the inclusion of VLOK, the relief of pain, dizziness, and ear noise occurred significantly faster - the average time of relief of clinical symptoms was 7.2 ± 2.1 days ($p < 0.01$), the average time of relief of clinical symptoms was 11.2 ± 1.8 days ($p < 0.01$).

Average time of relief of clinical symptoms in patients with HCG during treatment

Group Symptoms	Control group (n=15)	Main group (n=19)
Terms of pain relief, days	22,3±1,7	7,2±2,1 **
Terms of relief of noise in the ear, dizziness, days	21,4±1,6	11,2±1,8 **

** - p<0.01 compared to the control group.

In the questionnaire, a higher value in the scale corresponds to a better indicator of the quality of life. The analysis of patient questionnaires showed an initial decrease in the quality of life of patients with HCG compared to the healthy group in both the main and control groups on all 5 scales of the questionnaire (Table 3) - physical

functioning (PF), role functioning (RF), pain scale (BP) general health (GH), vitality (VT).

Dynamics of quality of life indicators according to the questionnaire in patients with HCG (points)

Questionnaire criteria	Healthy group	Observation points	Counter. group	Main group
PF	83,3±1,9	1	28,1±5,6**	26,04±6,3**
		2	20,0±3,1	48,7±4,2*
		3	48,6±3,8	58,2±3,8**
RF	73,3±5,9	1	18,0±3,3**	31,2±2,6***
		2	29,4±4,5	52,6±1,9***
		3	39,9±3,5*	58,1±2,3***
BP	71,8±3,0	1	24,1±3,7***	25,4±6,4***
		2	27,5±4,7	48,3±5,8**
		3	25,8±4,6*	59,2±5,2***
GH	60,8±4,9	1	29,2±5,6***	28,8±3,6**
		2	40,2±5,8	49,7±5,8
		3	42,6±4,9	52,2±5,9*
VT	59,1±3,8	1	31,5±6,3**	31,6±4,1***
		2	32,4±9,7	63,7±7,7**

		3	38,8±6,4	59,6±6,2**
		3	47,3±6,5**	58,5±5,2***

Note: * - p<0.05; ** - p<0.01; *** - p<0.001-differences with the healthy group.

Analysis of the questionnaire data two weeks after the start of treatment revealed a significant improvement in all indicators in patients with HCG in the main group against the background of VLOK, with the exception of the indicator of general health (GH), a significant change in which occurred after three months. These results indicate an increase in physical activity, an expansion of the daily activities of patients, an increase in the assessment of the state of health and vital activity, an improvement in the emotional state and the elimination of depressive, anxious experiences after the therapy.

At the preoperative stage, we evaluated the most relevant questions that cause anxiety and concern to the patient, based on the average values of the respondents' responses. They were the 1st, 3rd, 4th, 5th, questions. That is, the most exciting factors are the problem of communication, tinnitus, the need to protect the ear from water and take

medication. Dizziness and a feeling of discomfort in the ear are not so exciting for patients. Although, as you know, the most severe forms of HCG often begin with these symptoms.

In the control group, after treatment, significant dynamics were noted on the social functioning scale (SF) and three months later on the role-based physical functioning scale (RF) and the pain scale (BP).

Thus, intravenous laser blood irradiation accelerates the relief of the main clinical symptoms of the disease, reduces the frequency of relapses and improves the quality of life of patients with HCG.

Conclusions. It is shown that the inclusion of intravenous laser blood irradiation in the complex therapy of HCG after tympanoplasty reduces the activity of the disease and improves the quality of life of patients.

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ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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